

OBSERVER SHEET — DAY 2

Open-Ended Challenge: Transfer of Resilience

Case Study 3: Resilience Workshop | Blue Blocks Micro Research Institute | March 2026

Observer name	Team (A / B / C / D)	Number of children
Obs-1	(not specified)	C-10, C-07, C-11

THE CHALLENGE BRIEF (read aloud to all teams simultaneously)

You have these materials and 60 minutes. Your task is to design a system that solves this problem: water needs to move from one container to another without being poured directly, using only what is in front of you. There is no single correct answer. We have given you one cup of water to test with, but you can have as many cups and as much water as you want. Begin when you are ready.

Materials per team: two containers (different sizes), masking tape, ten A4 sheets, scissors, four plastic straws, two rubber bands, one small cup of water.

⚠ The first approach is designed to fail or partially fail. Do not tell the teams this.

Key observation for this session:

The brief does not specify which containers must be used, and children can request additional cups at any time. A child who re-reads the brief closely and notices what it does not say — and then asks for a small cup and uses a single bent straw — has solved the task with a qualitatively different kind of thinking than a child who works only with what is physically in front of them.

Section D (brief interrogation) and Section E (materials requested) are new to this version of the sheet and exist specifically to capture this. Do not prompt or hint — just observe and record.

SECTION A — Language at the moment of failure

When the team's first approach fails or partially fails, write down verbatim what is said. Note who speaks using a consistent identifier (seat position, letter, or number). Note the time. Do not interpret during the session.

Time	Verbatim quote or described behaviour	Observer notes (no interpretation yet)
1:52	Gave me a great idea	
1:30	There is a leak —	They used tape to secure the leak

SECTION B — How the team responds after failure

After the first failure, note what happens. Tick all that apply and describe what you observe.

Response type	What you observed (describe)
Iterate on the same idea (small change, same approach)	
Abandon and restart from scratch	✓ They changed tactic

Stop and discuss before doing anything	✓ They discussed
Ask each other questions rather than making statements	✓ But one person remained quiet
Look to an adult (eye contact, turning toward observer or researcher)	
Go quiet for a period before re-engaging	
One child takes the lead and redirects the group	
The group reaches a consensus before moving forward	

SECTION C — How failure is framed in language

Throughout the session, note any moment where a child names or characterises what is happening. Capture how they frame adversity — as a problem to solve, a puzzle to explore, something to blame, or something else. Tick the language type in the third column.

Time	Verbatim quote	Language type — tick one: Problem / Puzzle / Blame / Neutral / Other
1:54	It is spilling — Tape it	Puzzle

SECTION D — How children engage with the brief itself

This is one of the most analytically significant sections. Watch for any moment where a child reads, questions, or reinterprets the brief — especially noticing what it does not constrain. Record verbatim where possible. A child who spots that the brief does not specify which container, or who asks for extra cups having re-read the task, is showing a qualitatively different orientation to the problem.

Behaviour	Time	What you observed — verbatim if possible
Re-reads the brief aloud or silently (note which child, note when)		
Points out something the brief does NOT say (e.g. which container, how much water)	1:48	Which is container 1 & 2?
Asks a clarifying question about the brief to the group or to an adult	1:52	Can we use something else
Explicitly argues for a broader or narrower reading of the brief		
Notices the extra-cups option and raises it with the group	1:50	"Can we have more cups?"
Uses the brief to settle a disagreement within the group		

If no engagement with the brief was observed at any point, note that explicitly:

SECTION E — Materials requested beyond the starting set

Log every request for additional materials. A team that asks for extra cups may be thinking expansively about the problem. A team that never asks may not have realised they could, or may have decided the starting set was sufficient. Both are data.

Time	What they asked for	Who asked (child ID)	What prompted the request
1:45	More cups	C-10	Because I said "you can have as many cups as you want"

If no materials were requested, note that explicitly:

SECTION F — Recovery arc across the session

Log each distinct attempt the team makes. A new attempt begins when they meaningfully change approach — not just a minor physical tweak. The final column now captures what materials (if any) they requested for that attempt.

Attempt #	What they tried	How it failed / what stopped it	Who initiated the next move	Materials requested for this attempt
1	Poked a hole & put a straw in	Water spilled out	C-10 & C-07	Cups
2	Used tape to secure the leak	—	(same as above)	—

SECTION G — Help-seeking behaviour

Note every moment where a child seeks help or deliberately chooses not to. Only record what is clearly visible — do not infer.

Time	What the child said or did	Who they sought help from: peer / adult / no one — persisted alone
—	—	—

If no help-seeking occurred at any point, note that explicitly:

SECTION H — End of session notes

Answer these questions immediately after the session ends. Write before you discuss with the other observer.

1. Did the team succeed at the task?	Yes
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2. How many distinct approaches did they try? (count meaningfully different methods, not minor tweaks)	One idea — 2 attempts
3. At what point did the first partial success emerge? (note approximate time)	After the 1st attempt
4. Did any child interrogate the brief in a way that changed the team's direction? (describe)	No
5. Did the team ask for extra materials? If so, what, and did it change their approach?	Extra cups — they didn't use the bowls at all
6. In one sentence: was failure treated as a problem, a puzzle, or something else?	Puzzle
7. Which child drove the most pivots? Note their identifier.	C-10

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Open-Ended Challenge: Transfer of Resilience

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Observer name	Team (A / B / C / D)	Number of children
Obs-2	C-03, C-09, C-08	3

THE CHALLENGE BRIEF (read aloud to all teams simultaneously)

You have these materials and 60 minutes. Your task is to design a system that solves this problem: water needs to move from one container to another without being poured directly, using only what is in front of you. There is no single correct answer. We have given you one cup of water to test with, but you can have as many cups and as much water as you want. Begin when you are ready.

Materials per team: two containers (different sizes), masking tape, ten A4 sheets, scissors, four plastic straws, two rubber bands, one small cup of water.

⚠ The first approach is designed to fail or partially fail. Do not tell the teams this.

Key observation for this session:

The brief does not specify which containers must be used, and children can request additional cups at any time. A child who re-reads the brief closely and notices what it does not say — and then asks for a small cup and uses a single bent straw — has solved the task with a qualitatively different kind of thinking than a child who works only with what is physically in front of them.

Section D (brief interrogation) and Section E (materials requested) are new to this version of the sheet and exist specifically to capture this. Do not prompt or hint — just observe and record.

SECTION A — Language at the moment of failure

When the team's first approach fails or partially fails, write down verbatim what is said. Note who speaks using a consistent identifier (seat position, letter, or number). Note the time. Do not interpret during the session.

Time	Verbatim quote or described behaviour	Observer notes (no interpretation yet)
	Team work	
	C-09 — I got this	As C-09 is doing innovative trials
	C-03 — Can I dunk & spit in the bowl?	

SECTION B — How the team responds after failure

After the first failure, note what happens. Tick all that apply and describe what you observe.

Response type	What you observed (describe)
Iterate on the same idea (small change, same approach)	✓ Nope they are using new ideas
Abandon and restart from scratch	

Stop and discuss before doing anything	✓ Yes
Ask each other questions rather than making statements	
Look to an adult (eye contact, turning toward observer or researcher)	✓ Yes, they looked at me but sorted out themselves
Go quiet for a period before re-engaging	
One child takes the lead and redirects the group	✓ C-09 taking lead
The group reaches a consensus before moving forward	✓ The group is doing trial & error method

SECTION C — How failure is framed in language

Throughout the session, note any moment where a child names or characterises what is happening. Capture how they frame adversity — as a problem to solve, a puzzle to explore, something to blame, or something else. Tick the language type in the third column.

Time	Verbatim quote	Language type — tick one: Problem / Puzzle / Blame / Neutral / Other

SECTION D — How children engage with the brief itself

This is one of the most analytically significant sections. Watch for any moment where a child reads, questions, or reinterprets the brief — especially noticing what it does not constrain. Record verbatim where possible. A child who spots that the brief does not specify which container, or who asks for extra cups having re-read the task, is showing a qualitatively different orientation to the problem.

Behaviour	Time	What you observed — verbatim if possible
Re-reads the brief aloud or silently (note which child, note when)		
Points out something the brief does NOT say (e.g. which container, how much water)		
Asks a clarifying question about the brief to the group or to an adult		
Explicitly argues for a broader or narrower reading of the brief		
Notices the extra-cups option and raises it with the group		
Uses the brief to settle a disagreement within the group		

If no engagement with the brief was observed at any point, note that explicitly: (No entries recorded)

SECTION E — Materials requested beyond the starting set

Log every request for additional materials. A team that asks for extra cups may be thinking expansively about the problem. A team that never asks may not have realised they could, or may have decided the starting set was sufficient. Both are data.

Time	What they asked for	Who asked (child ID)	What prompted the request
	Straws + cups + tape + scissors	C-09 (1) + C-08 (2) + C-03 (3)	

If no materials were requested, note that explicitly:

SECTION F — Recovery arc across the session

Log each distinct attempt the team makes. A new attempt begins when they meaningfully change approach — not just a minor physical tweak. The final column now captures what materials (if any) they requested for that attempt.

Attempt #	What they tried	How it failed / what stopped it	Who initiated the next move	Materials requested for this attempt

SECTION G — Help-seeking behaviour

Note every moment where a child seeks help or deliberately chooses not to. Only record what is clearly visible — do not infer.

Time	What the child said or did	Who they sought help from: peer / adult / no one — persisted alone
	They kept on asking about the rules of the competition	Mentor (adult)

If no help-seeking occurred at any point, note that explicitly:

SECTION H — End of session notes

Answer these questions immediately after the session ends. Write before you discuss with the other observer.

1. Did the team succeed at the task?	They are doing great
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2. How many distinct approaches did they try? (count meaningfully different methods, not minor tweaks)	1+1+1+1+1 (5 approaches)
3. At what point did the first partial success emerge? (note approximate time)	2nd trial
4. Did any child interrogate the brief in a way that changed the team's direction? (describe)	Yes, but after my denial they found a way
5. Did the team ask for extra materials? If so, what, and did it change their approach?	Yes, but after my denial they found a way
6. In one sentence: was failure treated as a problem, a puzzle, or something else?	A PUZZLE
7. Which child drove the most pivots? Note their identifier.	C-09

Additional Observer Note:

The students did really well. C-09 took the lead followed by C-08 & C-03 and effectively applying Archimedes principle, core physics concepts, and innovation to make the project successful and well executed. — Obs-2

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Open-Ended Challenge: Transfer of Resilience

Case Study 3: Resilience Workshop | Blue Blocks Micro Research Institute | March 2026

Observer name	Team (A / B / C / D)	Number of children
Obs-3	C-06, C-01, C-12	3

THE CHALLENGE BRIEF (read aloud to all teams simultaneously)

You have these materials and 60 minutes. Your task is to design a system that solves this problem: water needs to move from one container to another without being poured directly, using only what is in front of you. There is no single correct answer. We have given you one cup of water to test with, but you can have as many cups and as much water as you want. Begin when you are ready.

Materials per team: two containers (different sizes), masking tape, ten A4 sheets, scissors, four plastic straws, two rubber bands, one small cup of water.

⚠ The first approach is designed to fail or partially fail. Do not tell the teams this.

Key observation for this session:

The brief does not specify which containers must be used, and children can request additional cups at any time. A child who re-reads the brief closely and notices what it does not say — and then asks for a small cup and uses a single bent straw — has solved the task with a qualitatively different kind of thinking than a child who works only with what is physically in front of them.

Section D (brief interrogation) and Section E (materials requested) are new to this version of the sheet and exist specifically to capture this. Do not prompt or hint — just observe and record.

SECTION A — Language at the moment of failure

When the team's first approach fails or partially fails, write down verbatim what is said. Note who speaks using a consistent identifier (seat position, letter, or number). Note the time. Do not interpret during the session.

Time	Verbatim quote or described behaviour	Observer notes (no interpretation yet)
	Enthusiastic	Observing the material given. Asking questions related to activity.

SECTION B — How the team responds after failure

After the first failure, note what happens. Tick all that apply and describe what you observe.

Response type	What you observed (describe)
Iterate on the same idea (small change, same approach)	✓ Yes
Abandon and restart from scratch	✓ Yes

Stop and discuss before doing anything	✓ Yes
Ask each other questions rather than making statements	✓ Simultaneous actions are happening
Look to an adult (eye contact, turning toward observer or researcher)	✓ Yes
Go quiet for a period before re-engaging	✓ Engaged in continuous discussion
One child takes the lead and redirects the group	✓ Two are engaged, the other doing actions
The group reaches a consensus before moving forward	✓ Three are in different approaches

SECTION C — How failure is framed in language

Throughout the session, note any moment where a child names or characterises what is happening. Capture how they frame adversity — as a problem to solve, a puzzle to explore, something to blame, or something else. Tick the language type in the third column.

Time	Verbatim quote	Language type — tick one: Problem / Puzzle / Blame / Neutral / Other
	Failure — Misunderstanding leads to new approach	No failure

SECTION D — How children engage with the brief itself

This is one of the most analytically significant sections. Watch for any moment where a child reads, questions, or reinterprets the brief — especially noticing what it does not constrain. Record verbatim where possible. A child who spots that the brief does not specify which container, or who asks for extra cups having re-read the task, is showing a qualitatively different orientation to the problem.

Behaviour	Time	What you observed — verbatim if possible
Re-reads the brief aloud or silently (note which child, note when)		Aloud
Points out something the brief does NOT say (e.g. which container, how much water)		
Asks a clarifying question about the brief to the group or to an adult		Yes, middle of activity
Explicitly argues for a broader or narrower reading of the brief		No argument is observed
Notices the extra-cups option and raises it with the group		Exactly for extra cups
Uses the brief to settle a disagreement within the group		

If no engagement with the brief was observed at any point, note that explicitly:

SECTION E — Materials requested beyond the starting set

Log every request for additional materials. A team that asks for extra cups may be thinking expansively about the problem. A team that never asks may not have realised they could, or may have decided the starting set was sufficient. Both are data.

Time	What they asked for	Who asked (child ID)	What prompted the request
	Rubber bands	C-06	To proceed in a faster way

If no materials were requested, note that explicitly:

SECTION F — Recovery arc across the session

Log each distinct attempt the team makes. A new attempt begins when they meaningfully change approach — not just a minor physical tweak. The final column now captures what materials (if any) they requested for that attempt.

Attempt #	What they tried	How it failed / what stopped it	Who initiated the next move	Materials requested for this attempt
1	Wide attempt	Mentor Instruction	3 together	No
2	Success model / Pressure Based model	It leads to understand mechanisms	C-06	No

SECTION G — Help-seeking behaviour

Note every moment where a child seeks help or deliberately chooses not to. Only record what is clearly visible — do not infer.

Time	What the child said or did	Who they sought help from: peer / adult / no one — persisted alone
	Asking questions for briefing the concept in the middle of making the model	From peer & adult took help. All 3 adolescents.

If no help-seeking occurred at any point, note that explicitly:

SECTION H — End of session notes

Answer these questions immediately after the session ends. Write before you discuss with the other observer.

1. Did the team succeed at the task?	Yes, with a meaningful model
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2. How many distinct approaches did they try? (count meaningfully different methods, not minor tweaks)	Three
3. At what point did the first partial success emerge? (note approximate time)	After 20 min of the start
4. Did any child interrogate the brief in a way that changed the team's direction? (describe)	Yes. Exactly happened for the brief.
5. Did the team ask for extra materials? If so, what, and did it change their approach?	Yes, they asked. Later restricted to available material. Adolescent took it as puzzle.
6. In one sentence: was failure treated as a problem, a puzzle, or something else?	Adolescent took it as puzzle
7. Which child drove the most pivots? Note their identifier.	C-01 — Model works.

OBSERVER GROUP 4 — Mentor Observations (Case Study 2) | Team: C-13, C-05, C-14

OBSERVER SHEET — DAY 2

Open-Ended Challenge: Transfer of Resilience

Case Study 3: Resilience Workshop | Blue Blocks Micro Research Institute | March 2026

Observer name	Team (A / B / C / D)	Number of children
(Innovation & Resilience Challenge — Case Study 2, Mentor Observations, Day 2)	C-13, C-05, C-14 (+ others)	(not specified)

THE CHALLENGE BRIEF (read aloud to all teams simultaneously)

You have these materials and 60 minutes. Your task is to design a system that solves this problem: water needs to move from one container to another without being poured directly, using only what is in front of you. There is no single correct answer. We have given you one cup of water to test with, but you can have as many cups and as much water as you want. Begin when you are ready.

Materials per team: two containers (different sizes), masking tape, ten A4 sheets, scissors, four plastic straws, two rubber bands, one small cup of water.

⚠ The first approach is designed to fail or partially fail. Do not tell the teams this.

Key observation for this session:

The brief does not specify which containers must be used, and children can request additional cups at any time. A child who re-reads the brief closely and notices what it does not say — and then asks for a small cup and uses a single bent straw — has solved the task with a qualitatively different kind of thinking than a child who works only with what is physically in front of them.

Section D (brief interrogation) and Section E (materials requested) are new to this version of the sheet and exist specifically to capture this. Do not prompt or hint — just observe and record.

SECTION A — Language at the moment of failure

When the team's first approach fails or partially fails, write down verbatim what is said. Note who speaks using a consistent identifier (seat position, letter, or number). Note the time. Do not interpret during the session.

Time	Verbatim quote or described behaviour	Observer notes (no interpretation yet)
1:50	"It's alright! Drink it. Remember what [mentor] mentioned. Ok my god. Let's do one more thing"	One of them is impatient and observes. One of them talking about Archimedes principle in British accent.

SECTION B — How the team responds after failure

After the first failure, note what happens. Tick all that apply and describe what you observe.

Response type	What you observed (describe)
Iterate on the same idea (small change, same approach)	✓ ✓ They have changed their idea drastically

Abandon and restart from scratch	✓ ✓ But in a different way
Stop and discuss before doing anything	✓ ✓ Check first & there is something then another team mate will guide her
Ask each other questions rather than making statements	
Look to an adult (eye contact, turning toward observer or researcher)	✓ ✓ Asking questions from old reference, asking whether this is allowed or not
Go quiet for a period before re-engaging	
One child takes the lead and redirects the group	✓ ✓ Going and asking mentors, giving other tasks, and trying different approach
The group reaches a consensus before moving forward	

SECTION C — How failure is framed in language

Throughout the session, note any moment where a child names or characterises what is happening. Capture how they frame adversity — as a problem to solve, a puzzle to explore, something to blame, or something else. Tick the language type in the third column.

Time	Verbatim quote	Language type — tick one: Problem / Puzzle / Blame / Neutral / Other
	"Remember the thingy which we have in the science lab. To Vaghu Sir ke sath kiye... The Greek guy thing. Ms. Jaisoan. So you remember what Vaghu Sir showed us with the pipe. 'We can't use the tissue?'"	Problem / Trying to arrive at a solution by bringing previous knowledge
	"Bade I think I am gonna fail. Go ahead bro! 'Child-X my stupid, idiot... Scar why did you use that'"	Blame / Problem

SECTION D — How children engage with the brief itself

This is one of the most analytically significant sections. Watch for any moment where a child reads, questions, or reinterprets the brief — especially noticing what it does not constrain. Record verbatim where possible. A child who spots that the brief does not specify which container, or who asks for extra cups having re-read the task, is showing a qualitatively different orientation to the problem.

Behaviour	Time	What you observed — verbatim if possible
Re-reads the brief aloud or silently (note which child, note when)	2:00 pm	"You know what others are doing. I saw it in one of the videos. Bro! this is very slow!"
Points out something the brief does NOT say (e.g. which container, how much water)		
Asks a clarifying question about the brief to the group or to an adult		"I didn't understand why don't we... (sip it a little bit ... it's working. Yarjie... it is not touching the water in the cup but we are not touching the cup)"

Explicitly argues for a broader or narrower reading of the brief		
Notices the extra-cups option and raises it with the group		
Uses the brief to settle a disagreement within the group		

If no engagement with the brief was observed at any point, note that explicitly:

SECTION E — Materials requested beyond the starting set

Log every request for additional materials. A team that asks for extra cups may be thinking expansively about the problem. A team that never asks may not have realised they could, or may have decided the starting set was sufficient. Both are data.

Time	What they asked for	Who asked (child ID)	What prompted the request
	Tissues, Jajori(?), straws, balloons	C-13	Because it wasn't working

If no materials were requested, note that explicitly:

SECTION F — Recovery arc across the session

Log each distinct attempt the team makes. A new attempt begins when they meaningfully change approach — not just a minor physical tweak. The final column now captures what materials (if any) they requested for that attempt.

Attempt #	What they tried	How it failed / what stopped it	Who initiated the next move	Materials requested for this attempt
1	Straws + two bowls	Not able to suck the straw; siphon and press the straw, check the height — without touching the bowl	C-05 & C-14	Straws — they cut the straw/attached it to another straw with tape

SECTION G — Help-seeking behaviour

Note every moment where a child seeks help or deliberately chooses not to. Only record what is clearly visible — do not infer.

Time	What the child said or did	Who they sought help from: peer / adult / no one — persisted alone
	Adolescents asked the physics mentor	Adult (human) to ask a concept related to physics

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If no help-seeking occurred at any point, note that explicitly:

SECTION H — End of session notes

Answer these questions immediately after the session ends. Write before you discuss with the other observer.

1. Did the team succeed at the task?	Yes
2. How many distinct approaches did they try? (count meaningfully different methods, not minor tweaks)	Twice
3. At what point did the first partial success emerge? (note approximate time)	(not recorded)
4. Did any child interrogate the brief in a way that changed the team's direction? (describe)	No
5. Did the team ask for extra materials? If so, what, and did it change their approach?	No
6. In one sentence: was failure treated as a problem, a puzzle, or something else?	Puzzle — they took it as a challenge and arrived at a solution
7. Which child drove the most pivots? Note their identifier.	C-13 — leadership; C-14 — executed; C-05 — observer/executed